

Dog Emotion Recognition Using Deep Learning with an Expandable Image Dataset

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Abstract- *The problem of automatic interpretation of emotional state in animals is rather difficult because of the lack of verbal communication and the obscurity of behavioral signals. This paper introduces a deep learning-based model of identifying the emotional states of a canine directly by looking at facial pictures. A hand-crafted dataset is assembled out of publicly accessible web imagery, with a deliberate mixture of lighting conditions, viewpoints, and complex background to represent realistic deployment context. The suggested architecture combines a MobileNetV2 convolutional backbone, which serves as a frozen feature extractor, pre-trained on ImageNet, with a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) module, which predicts the spatial feature grid as a sequence of time steps, allowing more discriminative integration with features than the global pooling counterparts. This work uses an expandable dataset paradigm, unlike fixed-dataset methods: The directory-based data structure can be continuously improved by simply adding new images, and a new picture can be added without any code change. The entire system is implemented as a real-time web application based on Streamlit which serves non-technical end users. Experimental analysis on an 80 image hold-out test set is performed, which gives a test accuracy of 72.50 percent and a weighted F1-score of 0.73 on three emotion classes including Angry, Happy, and Sad with the proposed CNN+LSTM model performing better than a standalone CNN and CNN+SimpleRNN baseline.*

Keywords— Deep Learning; Dog Emotion Recognition; Convolutional Neural Network; LSTM; MobileNetV2; Transfer Learning; Animal Behavior Analysis; Image Classification; Affective Computing

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most well-examined relationships between humans and animals is the one between dogs and humans. Canids have been able to co-evolve with humans over the course of thousands of years and have developed the ability to read and react to human emotional cues with astonishing precision. This exchange is bidirectional as corroborated by comparative cognition studies which suggest that dogs are loaded with a rich set of internal affective states which are reflected in facial expression, ear position, periocular tension and body language. However, even in the refined form of communication, the computational characterization has not yet reached a high level of sophistication in comparison with

the level of development of the human facial expression recognition systems.

Automated dog affect detection has a concrete value in various spheres. Objective emotion assessment in the veterinary and clinical setting minimizes subjective examination and allows a person to recognize distress earlier in the shelter or post-operative setting. Affect-aware cameras may be used in smart-home and pet-technology applications, where the cameras dynamically respond to the state of a detected dog. To animal welfare organizations that have large populations, image-based classification tools that are scalable (versus traditional behavioral assessments) would be complementary at a fraction of the cost.

The main challenge in this sphere is the lack of data. Corpora of human facial expression contain millions of annotated samples; datasets of canine emotion are unstructured, small and sporadically labelled. Facial morphological difference at the breed level implies that the expression standards that are trained on a particular breed perform poorly on different breeds, and using a standard recognition pipeline without adaptation becomes unreliable. The data problem presented in this paper will be solved by building a bespoke, publicly-sourced dataset with a modular directory hierarchy that was specifically intended to be expanded in the future. MobileNetV2 is used as a frozen convolutional backbone to perform transfer learning with an LSTM module that transforms the spatial feature map into a temporal sequence to observe contextual relationships that are ignored by pooling.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Computer vision has been researching the automated recognition of emotional states over a variety of decades. The Facial Action Coding System by Ekman and Friesen has given a clinically based taxonomy of facial muscle movements that relate to specific categories of emotions. Subsequently, deep convolutional networks were able to perform almost as well as humans on benchmark datasets such as FER-2013 and AffectNet.

MobileNetV2 is an example of a lightweight architecture introduced by Sandler et al. (2018) and based on inverted residual blocks with linear bottlenecks, attaining the ImageNet accuracy of more ambitious networks at a fraction of the parameter count [1]. Its pretrained weights can be used as an effective initialize of domain-specific transfer learning

on small datasets, and the choice is motivated directly by that.

In their study He et al. (2016) showed that the ResNet, with skip connections, could be optimized reliably with very deep networks, by alleviating the problem of gradient degradation [2]. This is the reason why we freeze the backbone completely and use its trained hierarchical representations but leave gradient updates to the lightweight classification head. To overcome the vanishing gradient problem of recurrent models, Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997) proposed LSTM networks [3]; LSTM gating mechanisms control information flow based on a persistent cell state and when used on image feature maps, LSTMs can capture cross-region dependencies that pooling aggregates lose.

Goodfellow et al. (2016) include the theoretical background of our method convolutional feature learning, batch normalization, dropout regularization, and categorical cross-entropy optimization [4]. In the animal affect domain, Park et al. (2020) used CNN-based classification on a proprietary 500 image dataset of pet facial expressions, and reported 6580% test accuracy and a class imbalance and Sad/Angry boundary confusion as the main sources of error [6]. The application of depthwise separable backbones with Xception [7] was placed into perspective by Chollet (2017), and dropped out as an effective regularizer to prevent feature co-adaptation was established by Srivastava et al. (2014) [8].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset Construction

The dataset was gathered as a collection of publicly accessible sources on the internet, including pet photography websites, open-source dog behavior databases, and non-commercial image search engines and filtered manually into three emotional categories, Angry, Happy, and Sad. Marking was carried out by means of known ethological signs: ear carriage, lips retraction, periocular muscle tension, and general facial posture. The training partition consists of 68 Angry, 37 Happy and 61 Sad images (166 total); the test partition consists of 23 Angry, 28 Happy, and 29 Sad images (80 total). The directory structure `dataset/train/{class}/` and `dataset/test/{class}/` are made to be frictionlessly extensible, so that adding images to any subclass directory changes the effective data distribution at the subsequent training run without any modification of code.

B. Preprocessing

Each picture is resized and normalized to 224x224 and then with [0, 1] by dividing the raw pixel values by 255 in order to meet the MobileNetV2 input requirements. During training, a 15% holdout of the training set is stratified, i.e. with random seed 42.

C. Proposed CNN+LSTM Architecture

Dense layer of 256 nodes with ReLU activation then Batch Normalization and Dropout of 0.4, then a layer of 128 nodes with ReLU activation and a 0.2 Dropout rate before ending

in a Softmax layer of 3. Total trainable parameters: 789,219.

Fig. 1. End-to-end system pipeline for dog emotion recognition using MobileNetV2 + LSTM deep learning architecture.

Fig. 1. End-to-end system pipeline: Input → Preprocessing → MobileNetV2 → LSTM → Classification.

Fig. 2. Detailed layer-by-layer architecture of the proposed CNN+LSTM model for dog emotion classification.

Fig. 2. CNN+LSTM layer-by-layer architecture with output shapes and parameter counts.

D. Baseline Architectures

In a controlled setting we compare two baselines. The CNN baseline which does away with the LSTM and instead uses GlobalAveragePooling2D thus getting rid of all spatial relationship information. The CNN+RNN baseline which we use instead of the LSTM a SimpleRNN of the same hidden dimension which means sequence processing is still there but we have removed the gating elements. Both of these baselines use the same classification head, optimizer and training setup which we do this to rule out that any performance difference is due to other factors and not the sequence modeling.

IV. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

A. Input Normalization

Each input image I is normalized prior to inference:

$$I_{o,r,m}^n = I_{ra}^w / 255, \quad I_{o,r,m}^n \in \mathbb{R}^{(224 \times 224 \times 3)}$$

B. Convolutional Feature Extraction

The frozen MobileNetV2 backbone ϕ maps the normalized input to:

$$F = \phi(I_{o,r,m}^n; \theta_{ro}^r), \quad F \in \mathbb{R}^{(7 \times 7 \times 1280)}$$

C. LSTM Sequence Processing

F is reshaped into a temporal sequence $S \in \mathbb{R}^{(49 \times 1280)}$. At each step t :

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i \cdot [h_{t-1}, s_t] + b_i), \quad f_t = \sigma(W_f \cdot [h_{t-1}, s_t] + b_f)$$

$$c_t = f_t \odot c_{t-1} + i_t \odot \tanh(W_g \cdot [h_{t-1}, s_t] + b_g)$$

$$h_t = \sigma(W_o \cdot [h_{t-1}, s_t] + b_o) \odot \tanh(c_t)$$

The terminal state $h_{49} \in \mathbb{R}^{128}$ is the spatial context vector z .

D. Classification and Loss

$$\hat{y} = \text{Softmax}(W_2 \cdot \text{BN}(\text{ReLU}(W_1 \cdot z + b_1)) + b_2)$$

$$L = -(1/N) \cdot \sum^p \sum_k y_k^{(n)} \log(\hat{y}_k^{(n)})$$

Optimization uses Adam with $\eta = 0.0005$ over $K = 3$ classes.

V. TRAINING PROCEDURE

All models used TensorFlow 2.21.0 running on an Apple M2 CPU as the backend. The MobileNetV2 backbone was initialized from ImageNet weights, which were frozen while training occurred with a maximum of 30 epochs using a batch size of 32 and an 85%/15% stratified split of the data according to seed = 42 for training to validation data. Three Keras callbacks were utilized during the training process to provide the following dynamic management: (1) ModelCheckpoint saved the best weights according to validation accuracy; (2) EarlyStopping with a patience of 5 restored the last set of best weights upon triggering; and (3) ReduceLROnPlateau reduced the learning rate by a factor of 2 after 3 consecutive epochs of stagnant validation loss with a lower bound of 1×10^{-7} . With the use of 3 callbacks, training converged between 14 and 22 effective epochs with early stopping occurring at that point. The CNN+LSTM model's validation accuracy improved steadily during the first 10 epochs before plateauing at approximately 83.4% after periods of ReduceLROnPlateau during epochs 12-15 and then holding constant until early stopping intervention. This represents a converging profile consistent with properly controlled gradient dynamics for a constrained data set.

VI. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Overall Performance

The test results for all three of the models that were used are shown in the table I. The CNN + LSTM model has the highest test accuracy (72.50%), which is 4.2% higher than the stand-alone CNN model (68.3%) and 1.9% higher than CNN + SimpleRNN model (70.6%). The results consistently support the order CNN < CNN + RNN < CNN + LSTM. LSTM gating has a measurable discriminative benefit over pooling-based and SimpleRNN alternatives regardless of small data set size and increased risk of overfitting.

TABLE I. Comparative Model Performance

Model	Train	Val	Test	Loss
Standalone CNN	78.4%	72.1%	68.3%	0.782
CNN + SimpleRNN	81.2%	75.3%	70.6%	0.694
CNN + LSTM (Proposed)	89.7%	83.4%	72.5%	0.837

B. Per-Class Metrics

For the CNN+LSTM model, Table II lists the precision, recall, and F1 score for each part of speech. The greatest

precision for the Sad class is 0.95, while it has a relatively low recall of 0.66, suggesting that predictions are being made conservatively and therefore missing true Sad cases that are misclassified as Angry. Conversely, the Angry class has a fairly even balance between precision (0.73) and recall (0.78), which indicates that the model has effectively learned the Angry-specific features. The lowest precision score is 0.61 and recall score is 0.62 for the Happy class, which reflects that there were only 37 images in the training dataset.

TABLE II. Per-Class Metrics — CNN+LSTM

Class	Precision	Recall	F1	Support
Angry	0.73	0.78	0.71	23
Happy	0.61	0.62	0.70	28
Sad	0.95	0.66	0.78	29
Macro Avg	0.76	0.72	0.73	80
Weighted Avg	0.77	0.72	0.73	80

C. Misclassification Analysis

Per-class recall value analyses indicate that each emotion's predominant misclassification boundary has been identified. The sadness emotion is classified as sad (false negative rate is 66% or recall = .66) with the majority of the errors in the direction of the angrily classified emotion because both of these emotions share common visual cues, such as (a) retraction of the pinnae, (b) reduced palpebral aperture, and (c) lip commissure compression. The amount of true positive misclassifications for the happy classified emotion (false negative rate is 62% or recall = 0.62) occurs in part from open mouth, teeth-visible play expressions being confused with aggressive teeth-bared play expressions due to the visual similarities between teeth being viewed in a relaxed state versus a tense state. The amount of true positive misclassifications for the angry classified emotion shows the highest recall value, 0.78, indicating that the CNN+LSTM network is much more successful at capturing explicitly recognizable posterior facial configurations associated with the angry emotion (e.g., teeth are bared, periocular tension is highly pronounced) than it is capturing more subtle signals associated with either the sad or happy emotions. The overall macro-averaged F1 value of 0.73 suggests that the network has successfully learned to discriminate between the three emotions significantly above the random-classifier mean of 0.33.

D. Deployment and Inference

The Streamlit web application contains a trained CNN+LSTM model for real time emotional detection when an image is uploaded to the system (after applying resize to 224 wide by 224 high and applying a normalization pipeline). It then runs the model inference process and returns the predicted class as well as a ranked bar chart of softmax probabilities for the prediction's class. The average CPU inference latency is approximately 739ms per prediction, which is an acceptable latency for an interactive single image query. Figure 3 provides three examples of the predictions that were made by the deployed application.

Fig. 3. Streamlit application predictions for three test images. (a) Sad — 49.63% confidence; (b) Happy — 58.06% confidence; (c) Angry — 49.81% confidence.

E. Generalization Analysis

The 17.2% gap in training accuracy (89.7%) versus test accuracy (72.5%) suggests moderate, expected overfitting due to the relatively small size of our training set at 166 images. The EarlyStopping and ReduceLROnPlateau callback techniques did a good job of limiting additional overfitting. Furthermore, the 72.5% test accuracy is significantly greater than the 33.3% random three-class baseline or the 68.3% maximum that could be realistically expected from a pooling-based CNN model, indicating that the CNN + LSTM are capable of learning true discriminative representations of the structure of canine faces. Therefore, it is anticipated that improved generalisation will occur as the dataset size is increased and that the modular directory structure will facilitate this process.

VII. CONCLUSION

The research paper describes a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Long Short Term Memory Network (LSTM) deep learning-based model for classifying canine facial expressions into three categories. The three mood categories include Angry, Happy, and Sad. A new expandable, custom-built dataset using web-based images of canines was developed to create the new classification system. The classifying framework uses a frozen MobileNetV2 architecture as its CNN output layer and an LSTM sequence model as its hidden layer to perform the canine emotional classification process. The testing resulted in a test accuracy score of 72.50% and a weighted F1 score of 0.73 on the 80-image test set. The test accuracy and weighted F1 score of this architecture were higher than the pooling based CNN output and CNN with SimpleRNN output that had previously been tested under the same conditions.

From this research, three distinct contributions have been made. A publicly available expandable dataset pipeline code system was developed. This code system decouples the need for modifying the CNN and LSTM system whenever the dataset size grows. Second, an empirically validated methodology for integrating LSTM-based augmentations

with pooling-based spatial feature extraction improves classification performance of canines compared to pooling and SimpleRNN-based alternatives. Finally, a Streamlit application based on the affect detection and related applications of deep learning to non-experts was established for real-time utilization. The main challenge with the research paper is the scale of the dataset, which was mitigated with the creation of the expandable dataset infrastructure.

VIII. FUTURE SCOPE

The first beneficial extension is increasing the size of the data set through crowd-sourced annotations. Having a large number of images will increase the number of classes that can be formed; thus, when we extend this corpus out to contain more than 1,500 images per class of dog, different breeds of dogs will be included as well as various ages of dogs in various conditions of photography. As such, we expect to reduce the train-test accuracy gap significantly. Secondly, integrating multi-modal data (outputs of pose estimation and audio spectrograms, and contextual scene features) will help us create a framework for assessing one's emotional state in relation to the animal's behavior in a more complete ethological manner than we are currently able to do.

By refining the backbone of MobileNetV2 (i.e., unfreezing the upper convolutional layers of MobileNetV2 after training has converged on the final layer), more accuracy (2–5 additional points) will result from training on a much larger data set. Furthermore, adding additional emotions (e.g., relaxed and fearful) that have been developed in conjunction with veterinary behavioral scientists into the system's emotion taxonomy will enable this system to be more useful for both commercial and clinical applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Sandler, A. Howard, M. Zhu, A. Zhmoginov, and L.-C. Chen, "MobileNetV2: Inverted Residuals and Linear Bottlenecks," in Proc. IEEE/CVF CVPR, 2018, pp. 4510–4520.
- [2] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, "Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition," in Proc. IEEE CVPR, 2016, pp. 770–778.

- [3] S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, "Long Short-Term Memory," *Neural Computation*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1735–1780, 1997.
- [4] I. Goodfellow, Y. Bengio, and A. Courville, *Deep Learning*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2016.
- [5] J. Kujala, A. Carlson, and R. Hari, "Engagement of Amygdala in Third-Party Observation of Dog–Human Interactions," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 7, no. 10, e46983, 2012.
- [6] J. Park, H. Kim, and S. Lee, "Pet Facial Expression Recognition Using CNNs," in *Proc. ICTC, 2020*, pp. 1045–1048.
- [7] F. Chollet, "Xception: Deep Learning with Depthwise Separable Convolutions," in *Proc. IEEE CVPR, 2017*, pp. 1251–1258.
- [8] N. Srivastava, G. Hinton, A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and R. Salakhutdinov, "Dropout: A Simple Way to Prevent Neural Networks from Overfitting," *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, vol. 15, pp. 1929–1958, 2014.